

COMPARING PC COST AND THE EFFECT OF BUSINESSES SIZE AND BUSINESSES REVENUE

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Abstract

This researches surveyed whether business size affects or is related to PC cost. Both the big business and the small business may have different cost volume and expenses relating to use of PC's. This is a current topical problem because many businesses owners want to know about the cost of PC's to help them understand the use of PC's across the business. This researches looked to find the connections between the size of the businesses (small or large) and the cost of the PC's. The researches survey the business in Zamboanga City and Davao City. The researches has found that the PC's cost does increase with businesses revenue and size. We also make some remarks for helping other business and future researches.

Introduction

Today there are many business using Personal Computers (PC's) for many business tasks including processing sales invoices, product and service orders, as well as electronic bookkeeping, financial management, accounting management and other tasks like this. Today, many businesses find the PC's are essential to their commercial transactions with the customers and other businesses partnerships. The PC use is growing in many areas of the business for usefulness and employee satisfaction.

But recently there have been some debates among the press and business leaders about whether the size of the business will affect the cost of implementation in PC's across the business and if this could be lower. After the Electronic Commerce Act (Republic Act 8792) many business wish to know the cost of how their technology are doing for business opportunities. So there is a pressure on business to make better economical decision for the PC's.

The main problem to be investigated in this researches is that the business with the PC's may be paying greater costs and these costs may be different if they are the big business or the small business. This researches aim to determine if PC's are more expensive to use in big business with the greater staff numbers and greater revenue. Greater revenue also may need better

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business management. Staff and employees using the PC have greater need for accessing the processing power today and so we need to determine whether the cost of these is higher.

For this researches we conducted a survey of businesses in the greater Western Mindanao region. The survey show that some businesses in the region are better users of PC's at greater employee and revenue numbers.

Prior Research on PC's Use

It is common today for business of all kinds of industry to be using the PC for a wide range of business process. Customers and partners expect business services to be modern for e-business use to flourish. Research by Jutla et al. (2001) show that retaining customers depends on having a good personal computer strategy that will also help the e-business. Also, research from Korner and Zimmerman (2000) shows that information and communication technology (ICT) is growing among business and this is helping them to take advantage of e-business.

This e-business support comes at a price for the business. Having a personal computer for each employee helps to improve the amount of e-business support but also increases operating costs for the business.

Greater PC use also increases the cost of e-business support by making the technology more expensive for the business. Management are also required to keep the technology going and therefore businesses can expect to pay more for maintenance in addition.

Keeping these costs low is important to the business. Many businesses are worried that they need to spend too much to operate and maintain these personal computers and are wondering whether there is value.

Businesses Size

The size of the business affects the cost to operate the business functions. A small business is not the same as a big business. Rensleigh and Olivier (1998) explained that affordability and cost have different effects in small business than big business. Big businesses may have more employees for managing all the services and business operation in the company. But small business depend on sharing employee task within the business to save resources. The big business often has more business employees and big business may be more bureaucratic (Stott and Wood 2001).

In a big business, more employees may have PC's, to improve e-business support. Big business may have more business undertaking and the variety of task also mean more PC's in the use. Small business may be more focus on the particular task in e-business. The focus have a narrow effect on the e-business service and the business operation. It also need the special expertise to keep the PC's going which means the additional cost is higher for them (Gill and Pidduck 2001).

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Also big business has more revenue from the business operation. Big business extent of work is greater and more operation. More transaction with the customer even include the e-business produce more transaction and business revenue. Therefore the big business can also have the greater revenue.

In the study of business size there are two ways to measure the size of the business. These measures are needed for the hypothesis in the research. One way is to measure the number of business employees and the other way is to measure the revenues of the business (Goode 2001). To ensure that we are properly measuring the business size, the researches use both of these measures.

Business with more business employees have higher business cost because it cost them to employ the people for e-business. And the business with more employees have higher PC's cost. The hypothesis means:

Hypothesis 1- Business with greater business size have higher PC's cost.

Business may make more profit with the PC's than without the PC's. The hypothesis means:

Hypothesis 2- Business with higher business revenue have higher PC's cost.

Research Methodology

The common research methodology is the business survey. This research used a business survey for the data collection. The research project contacted 300 business to participate in our survey about PC's cost in the business. The survey targeted the businesses of greater Western Mindanao region including Zamboanga City and Davao City.

110 business kindly replied about the PC use and cost, and also the servers for file hosting and databases. This meant a survey response rate of 36% in total.

As far as industry type is concern, 22 sample members were in fishing and seafood manufacturing industries, 45 sample members were in the retail industry, 10 were in diverse services industry. Two of the survey sample members did not divulge their industry.

Table 1 give the demographic information of the survey members. All of the sample members used PC's but there was a difference in the number of the PC's for each business employee. The data in the table show that there is a range of numbers of employees working in the business. The small business are important to the business group of the economy and popular in the market area.

Table 1. Demographic Information of the Survey Business

Business Type	Number	Percent
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Business Type	Number	Percent
Retailers	45	40.9
Fishing and seafood manufacturing	22	20
IT	16	14.5
Food and beverages	15	13.6
Diverse services	10	9
Not stated	2	1.8
Total	110	100
Business Size	Number	Percent
1-10 employees	23	20.9
10-20 employees	41	37.2
20-30 employees	26	23.6
30-40 employees	16	14.5
40-100 employees	4	3.6
Total	110	100

The researcher analysed the data from the survey sample members and compared the employee and revenue data of the sample members to the expenditure on PC's. First, we analysed the employees size, given in the first figure 1. The chart shows that most business spend less than around ₱200,000 yearly but some of the sample members spend much more than that. This mean that most businesses in this group spend about ₱10,000 to ₱20,000 on account for each employees in the business to support e-business. Also there are other business that have greater employees while spending little on the PC's.

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Figure 1. Business size and PC's cost

Second we have analyse the revenues size in the second figure 2. The chart shows that most survey business have less than around ₱1,000,000 revenue according to the sample. But some business have lower PC's cost even with the revenues at the same level.

Figure 1 Business revenues and PC's Cost

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The researches analyses show that the business size relate to the cost of the PC's. If the business is big, the cost of the PC's is higher. If the business is small, the cost of the PC's is lower. But the measurements of the business size change the impact of the PC's cost in the result. In the number of employees the result is different to the revenues size. The size may affect the first-mover advantage in competition (Brown 2001).

Cost Drivers

The sample member explain the cost driver for the PC's in the business. There are a variety of cost driver in e-business service for the business. The survey sample explain to use the example of these costs:

- PC training costs
- Software costs
- Hardware and installation costs
- Consumable costs (printer cartridge, etc)
- Network cabling costs
- PC's administration costs
- Repair costs
- Running costs
- Planning costs

The cost of PC's in the business must be managed and it is a responsibility of the accounting staff for cost management (Crospey et al. 1990). This responsibility for accounting has to work hand in hand for managing the e-business cost throughout the business. There is difficulty in keeping track of all the c-business costs including the web server and HTML (Goldszmidt et al. 2001). So the e-business cost would be higher.

Conclusion

In this research we have looked at the cost for PC's in small business. We survey the business in greater Western Mindanao region particularly Zamboanga City and Davao City. The study show that PC's cost increase with businesses employees and businesses revenue. PC's help the business operation but also increase the cost for the managers.

The research project is continuing and we are hoping to study also the role of e-business cost in the business. Because the e-business cost may be different to the traditional PC's cost. We plan to use the traditional business measures to examine the new e-business relationship.

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